

A comparative study on electrodeposition of Fe-W-B and Fe-Mo-B alloys

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Electrodeposition processes for depositing boron-containing iron-tungsten and iron-molybdenum alloys on copper cathode from baths having ferrous sulfate, sodium tungstate (or molybdate), boron phosphate, ammonium citrate, 1-dodecylsulfate-Na and ammonia or sulfuric acid for pH adjustments have been developed. Bath stability, cathode current efficiency and quality of deposit of molybdenum alloy are more satisfactory than those of tungsten alloy. The current efficiency of tungsten alloy deposition is improved by increasing the bath temperature but no advantage of higher temperature is found for deposition of the molybdenum alloy.

In spite of numerous claims, the electrodeposition of tungsten as well as of molybdenum in pure state from aqueous solutions has been unsuccessful¹. But their electrolytic induced codeposition occurs with iron-group metals². The most important of the early researches on the deposition of tungsten- and molybdenum-alloys were the work of Goltz and Kharlamov³. They used ammoniacal plating solutions and the deposits obtained were porous and weak. The next development was the use of organic hydroxy acids in these ammoniacal baths to yield more stable baths of much higher concentrations⁴. The alloys deposited were crystalline. More recently Watanabe⁵ has reported electrodeposition of several amorphous alloys. The literature reveals that under proper conditions of bath composition, voltage and current parameters, an amorphous layer may be deposited on a cathode by electrodeposition^{5,6}. But for the most part the electrodeposition of amorphous alloys of these metals has been limited to a few demonstration systems of little direct practical interest, and there are no known instances of electrodeposition of high hardness, wear resistance, moderately ductile amorphous alloys^{2,7}.

Thus there is a need for a process for preparing coatings of high hardness, wear-resistant, corrosion-resistant and moderately ductile amorphous alloys by electrodeposition. The work on development, optimization and control of baths for producing such amorphous alloys has therefore been undertaken. The results on electrodeposition of Co-W-B and Ni-W-B have already been reported from this laboratory⁸. The initial work on electrodeposition of Fe-W-B and Fe-Mo-B has been presented recently⁹.

Results and Discussion

Fe-W-B alloys : Based on the results of several experi-

ments the following bath composition was selected for studying the effect of different parameters on deposition of the alloy : 0.26 M FeSO₄·7H₂O, 0.10 M Na₂WO₄·2H₂O, 0.15 M BPO₄, 0.55 M (NH₄)₂C₆H₆O₇, 1.04 × 10⁻⁴ M 1-dodecylsulfate-Na and pH 9.0. The electrodeposition was performed at 25° on a copper cathode rotating at 10 rpm and maintained at a constant current density of 35 mA cm⁻². The alloy deposited was sound, smooth and partially amorphous having metallic luster with an average composition of 47% W, 51% Fe and 2% B. The maximum current efficiency for the deposition was around 18%. The pH of the bath and operating parameters had significant effect on the deposition results, which are discussed below.

The plots of pH change on the cathode current efficiency for deposition of the alloy showed that significantly acidic or basic baths are not suitable for this system. In the acidic baths (pH ≤ 4) the hydrogen discharge seems to be the main cathodic reaction whereas in basic media (pH ≥ 10) the precipitation of iron hydroxide is probable explanation for the low efficiency. The alloy deposited at pH 9 was more sound and smooth having better adherence. There was a minimum in the efficiency curve at pH 8, coinciding with the region where tungsten content of the alloy was higher. The effect is probably related partly to variation in cathode current efficiency of deposition of iron and partly to the formation of citrate complexes¹⁰.

It was found that a good quality coating could be achieved at a relatively narrow range of cathode current densities. The lower range of the preferred current density turned out to be above the hydrogen overvoltage of the cathode and it is postulated that the nascent hydrogen may be involved in the reduction of the tungstate complex. The

best operating current density was found to be 35 mA cm^{-2} , below which the deposits tend to be completely crystalline in structure. The current densities higher than this resulted in burnt deposits of gray to dark colors.

The electrodeposition was studied in the temperature range $25\text{--}80^\circ$. The current efficiency increased with the temperature. However, the stability of the bath decreased at higher temperatures. The presence of ammonium ions was found to increase the bath stability. An addition of 9 g/l $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ stabilized the bath, although at a lower concentration of ferrous sulfate (0.1 M in place of 0.26 M). In spite of the lower iron concentration the current efficiency at 70° (21%) was higher than at 25° (18%). This increase in current efficiency with temperature confirms that the reduction of iron is a diffusion-controlled process¹¹.

The plot of the effect of cathode rotation on the current efficiency showed two peaks, the one at 10 rpm and the other at 20 rpm. The alloy deposited at 10 rpm was found homogeneous, sound and with metallic luster and having more acceptable characteristics than the deposit obtained at any other rotation rate. The decrease in current efficiency around 15 rpm may be ascribed to the kinetic correlation of codeposition of iron, tungsten and hydrogen. Tungsten deposition is activation-controlled whereas iron and hydrogen discharge is diffusion-controlled¹¹. It may be presumed that in these conditions, as the cathode rotation speed increases from 10 to 15 rpm, the concentration of tungstate ions within the cathodic layer is also increased, the formation of lower-valency tungsten compounds thus being easier. The latter compounds block the cathode surface and consequently, the percentage of tungsten in the coating is decreased. A black bloom arising on the cathode surface in such conditions supports this mechanism. A similar effect was observed with increased sodium tungstate concentration in the bath. This abnormal effect, i.e. the process rate lowering with higher rotation, may also be correlated to an intermediate active product being formed during the process and taking part in indirect reactions on the electrode (cathode surface blockage by lower-valency compounds of tungsten and by iron hydroxides).

Fe-Mo-B alloys : The bath developed for electrodeposition of Fe-W-B was modified to get a deposit of Fe-Mo-B alloy with desirable characteristics. Sodium tungstate was substituted by sodium molybdate. In contrast to the tungsten alloy plating baths the presence of ammonium salts in the molybdenum baths had detrimental effect on the deposit. They caused decrease in current efficiency and the deposits were loose and grayish black. Ammonium citrate was therefore substituted by sodium citrate. Based on a series of experimental results the final bath composi-

tion selected was : $0.26 \text{ M FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $0.10 \text{ M Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.15 M BPO_4 , $0.55 \text{ M Na}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_7$ and $1.04 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ 1-dodecylsulfate-Na.

The study of pH variation on deposition of the alloy gave a peak in cathode current efficiency at pH 6.0. An increase in the bath pH beyond 6.0 showed a gradual fall in the deposition efficiency which may be ascribed to some changes occurring in nature of the metallic complexes present in the bath¹². Lowering the pH of the bath below 3.0 led to the formation of dark red lower valent soluble species, in which molybdenum was probably trivalent¹³. The best-appearing deposit was obtained at pH 6.0.

The studies on temperature effect on deposition of the molybdenum alloy did not show any advantage in working at elevated temperatures. It was noted that the operation at 70° resulted in dark and nonmetallic deposits. While working at 25° , a cathode rotation of 30–35 rpm was required for reducing the thickness of the cathode diffusion layer. At rotation rates lower than this the current efficiency was found to be poorer.

The effect of cathode current density showed that there was not any metallic deposition below 17 mA cm^{-2} . Hydrogen evolution could not take place at such a low current density, the evolution of which seems to be necessary for electrodeposition of induced-type deposition of molybdenum alloys⁶. The increase in current density to 100 mA cm^{-2} attained the maximum current efficiency (40%) for obtaining the deposit with acceptable characteristics. At current densities superior to 100 mA cm^{-2} the tensile stress in the deposit was found to increase resulting in decreased adhesion and formation of cracks.

After optimization of the bath composition and the operating parameters, it was found that the bath with $0.26 \text{ M FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $0.10 \text{ M Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.15 M BPO_4 , $0.55 \text{ M Na}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{O}_7$, $1.04 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ 1-dodecylsulfate-Na and pH 6.0 functioning at 25° and 100 mA cm^{-2} cathode current density and the copper cathode rotating at 35 rpm gave a deposit of acceptable characteristics. The alloy deposited had an average composition of 56% Mo, 42.5% Fe and 1.5% B and was sound, thick, partially amorphous and adherent to the substrate. The bath stability, cathode current efficiency and quality of the deposit of the molybdenum alloy were superior to those of the tungsten alloy.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade. Deionized distilled water was used for preparation of the solutions.

Alloys with high tungsten (molybdenum) and boron contents would be most desired for practical applications. Early baths¹⁴ for crystalline Fe-W alloys were modified to

get higher concentrations of tungsten in the deposits. Boron phosphate was incorporated in the bath to provide a source of boron for creating amorphous nature to the deposit. Boron content was kept as high as possible consistent with solubility. The concentrations of iron and tungsten were kept as high as possible consistent with remaining soluble at proper mole ratio. Ammonium citrate was added as complexing agent for stability of the bath. Its optimum concentration for the bath was determined experimentally. 1-Dodecylsulfate-Na was added as a wetting agent to reduce hydrogen pitting. pH of the bath was adjusted with ammonia or sulfuric acid.

The electrodeposition was realized on a copper sheet cathode (2.0–2.5 cm² surface area) rotated at a constant rate (EG & G 616 rotor) using a platinum foil (15 cm²) as anode, potentiostat (Amel 555B) as a source of potential and a thermostat (MTA KUTESZ MD2). The cathode was polished on Carimate papers with decreasing grit size and finished on alumina powder of 1 and 0.3 μm. The nature of the deposit was verified by X-ray diffraction and the composition of the deposit was determined by atomic absorption spectroscopy.

A large number of electrodeposition experiments was realized for optimization of the bath composition and the operating parameters. The experiments were performed by using the following ranges : cathode current density, 10–200 mA cm⁻², cathode rotation, 5–30 rpm; bath temperature, 25–80°C; bath pH 2–10. After every 20 min of the deposition the cathode was dried, weighed and analyzed. The bath developed for electrodeposition of Fe-W-B was modified to get a deposit of Fe-Mo-B alloy with desirable characteristics. Sodium tungstate was substituted by sodium molybdate. As ammonium ions in the bath showed detrimental effect on the deposit the complexing agent ammonium citrate was substituted by sodium citrate. A series of electrodeposition experiments, similar to those of the tungsten alloy deposition, was realized to determine the optimum bath composition and operating parameters.

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